

1 **Evaluation of acid fracturing in carbonatite geothermal reservoirs based on a**
2 **coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical-chemical model considering discrete fracture**
3 **networks**

4 **Abstract** In the development of carbonate geothermal reservoirs, the implementation
5 of acid fracturing technology is common and essential, effectively enhancing reservoir
6 permeability. It encompasses a sequence of intricate phenomena including solute
7 migration, acid-rock reaction, heat transfer, and deformation. Herein, a comprehensive
8 thermo-hydro-mechanical-chemical coupling model considering field-scale discrete
9 fracture networks (DFN) is established for the process. With the thin elastic layer and
10 fracture element assumptions, the corrosion and deformation of fractures are considered
11 simultaneously. Additionally, the model accounts for the corrosion effects of both
12 bedrock and fracture surfaces, and tracks the evolution of fracture aperture and matrix
13 porosity. Using the proposed model, this study investigates acid fracturing in varying
14 reservoir and operational conditions. It is found that the connectivity of DFN can
15 influence the seepage path of acid fluid, therefore affecting acid concentration transport,
16 which has a significant impact on the reconstruction of reservoir acidification. The
17 acidification effectiveness nonlinearly positively correlates to the rate and
18 concentration of acid injection, while the change of chemical aperture is negatively
19 correlated to the initial fracture aperture. Reservoir temperature has a limited influence
20 on acidification outcomes. The scientific insights provided here are valuable in steering
21 the optimization of acid fracturing in carbonatite reservoirs.

22 **Keywords:** acid fracturing, carbonatite geothermal reservoir, thermo-hydro-
23 mechanical-chemical coupling, discrete fracture network

24 1. Introduction

25 Geothermal energy, a clean, efficient, and sustainable energy source, is gradually
26 gaining attention from countries grappling with energy scarcity challenges and
27 responding to the imperatives of climate change[1-2]. The development of geothermal
28 resources has emerged as an important strategy to expedite the transition and
29 optimization of the energy mix as well as to achieve the goal of "carbon emission
30 reduction"[3-4]. Among the categories of hydrothermal reservoirs, carbonatite
31 geothermal reservoir constitutes a critical type, and the widespread utilization of which
32 has evolved into a focal point for future endeavors in geothermal exploration and
33 development[5-8]. Besides the recent increase in the scale of geothermal energy
34 development, equal emphasis should also be placed on enhancing the efficiency of
35 exploitation[9-11]. Currently, various fracturing processes are being employed to
36 improve the production rate including hydraulic fracturing, acid fracturing, sand
37 addition fracturing, and high-energy gas fracturing[12-13]. Notably, among these
38 techniques, the acid fracturing approach holds substantial importance for the
39 enhancement of carbonatite geothermal systems[14-15]. Acid fracturing uses the
40 injection of acid or acid pre-liquid from the casing at a displacement surpassing the
41 reservoir's capacity, thus rapidly establishing wellbore pressure that exceeds the
42 compressive stress of the formation and the tensile strength of the rock[16-18]. This

43 process leads to the fragmentation of the formation and the creation of fractures.
44 Continuous acid injection serves to extend these fractures, resulting in acid-etched
45 fissures characterized by enhanced diversion capacity compared to the original
46 formation. This not only augments the production capacity of the geothermal well but
47 also bolsters its backfilling capability.

48 To date, acid fracturing technology has consistently attracted considerable interest.
49 Ma and his research team proposed a Thermo-Hydro-Chemical (THC) coupling model
50 which adopts the unified pipe network method to simulate the process of acid fracturing
51 [19-21], where the interaction between stress and THC coupling is ignored. Liu et al.
52 [22-24], Mahmoodi et al. [25], and Babaei et al. [26] demonstrated through parameter
53 sensitivity analysis that the acid fracturing effect notably influences the formation and
54 expansion of wormholes. Guo et al. [27] summarized that the heat generated by the
55 rock-acid reaction can change the temperature distribution in fractures. Further, Li et al.
56 [28] introduced a Thermo-Hydro-Mechanical-Chemical (THMC) coupling model and
57 subsequently obtained the distribution of acid concentration and fracture width after the
58 acid fracturing process. Zhu et al. [29-30] established another coupled THMC model
59 appropriately incorporating the influence of heat generation during the rock-acid
60 reaction on the reaction rate which in turn affects the chemical process. There is also a
61 THMC model that effectively considers the field scale and obtains the spatial and
62 temporal distributions of critical parameters such as acid concentration and
63 permeability[31-33]. In addition, Song et al.[34-36] applied a THMC model to

64 investigate the influence of factors including chemical corrosion and precipitation,
65 injection concentration, and injection velocity on the evolution of fracture apertures. It
66 is supposed that one of the keys to optimizing the development of geothermal resources
67 hinges on the exploration of the THMC coupling mechanism[37-40].

68 In this process, understanding the multiple physical properties of geothermal
69 reservoirs is crucial. Specifically, the interactions among temperature, stress, porosity,
70 and fluid flow within geothermal systems influence energy transfer and reservoir
71 extraction efficiency. Therefore, studying the complex structure and behavior of
72 geothermal reservoirs aids in the accurate prediction of their thermodynamic properties
73 and development potential. Note that a discrete fracture network (DFN) is crucial in
74 understanding a geothermal reservoir, as the network identifies the flow of geothermal
75 fluids, which has been explored by several studies. Employing DFN, Hu et al.[41]
76 demonstrated that enhanced connectivity of fracture networks significantly improves
77 the distribution of solute concentration. Yang et al.[42] integrated discrete fracture
78 models with equivalent continuum models to analyze the impact of fracture variation
79 on fluid flow in heterogeneous subsurface tight reservoirs. A coupled THM model with
80 an embedded DFN model was proposed by Liao et al.[43] to simulate the complex flow
81 behaviors and thermal performance during CO₂ injection, indicating the significance of
82 DFN in analyzing flow features, heat flow, and fracture deformation. In addition, Xie
83 et al.[44] utilized a non-Darcy rough DFN model to describe the channel flow features
84 within fracture networks as well as the thermal-induced fracture propagation during

85 heat extraction, illustrating the effectiveness of the DFN model in capturing complex
86 THM coupling processes. Further, in the research of geothermal reservoirs with natural
87 fractures, DFN is efficient for simulating the fracture behavior and distribution. Zhao
88 et al.[45] applied the DFN model to accurately explain the behavior and distribution of
89 natural fractures, presenting their notable influence on stress variation and damage
90 evolution. It is indicated by Jiang et al.[46] that DFN plays a crucial role in optimizing
91 heat extraction strategies for fractured geothermal reservoirs and in mitigating seismic
92 risks. Also, in carbonate reservoirs, the implementation of DFN enables researchers to
93 investigate the presence, aperture, and distribution of fractures, as well as the sensitivity
94 of the dissolution process to acid injection rates, consequently disclosing the
95 remarkable impact of fracture structure on reactive flow[14, 47]. Nonetheless, the
96 function of DFN characteristics for the acid fracturing process in carbonatite
97 geothermal rock is seldom thoroughly explored within the context of the THMC
98 coupling model. In the current study, a fully coupled THMC model considering DFN
99 characteristics is innovatively proposed to investigate the chemical corrosion and
100 mechanical deformation of fractures during acid fracturing in carbonatite geothermal
101 reservoirs.

102 The arrangement of other sections is as follows. The multi-physics coupling model
103 is explained in Section 2 which considers the flow of acidizing fluid, transport of
104 reaction diluted species, heat transfer, deformation of rock matrix and fracture, along
105 with chemical corrosion for rock. Subsequently, Section 3 outlines the detailed

106 implementation steps of the proposed model and conducts model verification which
107 yields good validation results. Further, Section 4 proceeds with a series of numerical
108 simulations and explores parameter sensitivity. Lastly, conclusions are drawn in Section
109 5.

110 2. Theoretical modeling

111 Fig. 1 illustrates the multi-physics process of acid fracturing in a carbonatite
112 geothermal reservoir. The operational fluid comprising acidified mixed liquids is
113 injected into the fracture in a certain direction (e.g. from left to right in the schematic)
114 and undergoes a chemical reaction with the bedrock through the fracture. This reaction
115 leads to the increase of the aperture width which consequently augments the inflow
116 capacity of the reservoir. To simulate the above-mentioned process, this study
117 introduces a THMC model that couples the flow of acidizing fluid, transport of reaction
118 diluted species, heat transfer, mechanical deformation of rock matrix and fracture, as
119 well as chemical corrosion for rock. Owing to the relatively small aperture width, the
120 Reynolds number is considered to be small enough so that the operational fluid, which
121 is treated in the single liquid phase, performs a laminar flow ruled by Darcy's law, and
122 thus, the fracture permeability can be estimated by cubic law. It is also assumed that
123 fluid pressure, fluid temperature, and the concentration of chemical species exhibit
124 uniform distribution in the direction perpendicular to the thin fracture. Hence, the
125 corresponding values of variables at the upper and lower interfaces between the fracture
126 and bedrock are effective. Notably, the mass and heat transfer in the fracture as well as

127 its deformation in the 2-D space are simulated through 1-D fracture elements.

128

129 *Fig. 1 Schematic of acid fracturing in carbonate geothermal reservoirs including a single fracture (rock in blue*
 130 *color, fracture in gray with aperture width d_f , σ_n the normal stress, \mathbf{n}_u the normal vector at rock-fracture interface*
 131 *towards rock, \mathbf{n}_d the normal vector at rock-fracture interface towards fracture, \mathbf{k}_n the stiffness of rock in a normal*
 132 *direction and \mathbf{k}_s stiffness of rock in the transverse direction)*

133 2.1 Acidizing fluid flow

134 The mass conservation equations governing acidizing fluid flow in porous rock
 135 matrix and fracture are expressed in the following two equations, respectively[48].

$$136 \quad \rho_{acid} S_m \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{acid} \mathbf{v}_m) = -\rho_{acid} \alpha_{Bm} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{vm}}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

$$137 \quad d_f \rho_{acid} S_f \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\tau} \cdot (d_f \rho_{acid} \mathbf{v}_f) = Q_p - d_f \rho_{acid} \alpha_{mf} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{vf}}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

138 where ρ_{acid} is the density of the acidizing fluid, S the storage coefficient with
 139 subscripts, “ m ” and “ f ” indicating the matrix and the fracture, respectively, p the
 140 pressure, t the time, \mathbf{v} the fluid velocity vector, α_B the Biot-Willis coefficient, ε_v
 141 the volumetric strain, d_f the size of fracture aperture, Q_p the mass flux from matrix
 142 into fracture, and ∇ the gradient operator.

143 Following Darcy’s law, the velocities of acidizing fluid in the porous rock matrix
 144 and fracture can be obtained as follows.

145
$$\mathbf{v}_m = -\frac{k_m}{\mu_{acid}}(\nabla p - \rho_{acid} \mathbf{g}) \quad (3)$$

146
$$\mathbf{v}_f = -\frac{k_f}{\mu_{acid}}(\nabla_{\tau} p - \rho_{acid} \mathbf{g}) \quad (4)$$

147 where k is the permeability, μ the viscosity, and \mathbf{g} the gravitational acceleration.

148 The mass flux of fluid flow from the rock matrix into the fracture can be computed

149 using the following equation with the normal vectors, \mathbf{n}_u , and \mathbf{n}_d , given in Fig. 1.

150
$$Q_p = \mathbf{n}_u \cdot \left(-\rho_{acid} \frac{k_m}{\mu_{acid}} \nabla p \right) \Big|_{up} + \mathbf{n}_d \cdot \left(-\rho_{acid} \frac{k_m}{\mu_{acid}} \nabla p \right) \Big|_{down} \quad (5)$$

151 As laminar flow in thin aperture, the upper and lower variations are considered

152 negligible throughout this study.

153 2.2 Chemical reaction and transport of reaction diluted species

154 The main component of the rock in a carbonatite geothermal reservoir (e.g.

155 limestone) is calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). It can react with hydrochloric acid (HCl),

156 which is normally used in the fracturing process, as shown below.

158 Based on Eq. (6), it is demonstrated that one mole of HCl can dissolve half a mole

159 of CaCO_3 . To describe the chemical reaction, the variables of HCl are used as a basis,

160 and its transport in a porous matrix is governed by

161
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\phi_m C^{HCl}) + \mathbf{v}_m \cdot \nabla C^{HCl} - \nabla \cdot (D_e \nabla C^{HCl}) = -R_m^{HCl} \quad (7)$$

162 where ϕ_m the porosity of the rock matrix, C^{HCl} is the concentration of HCl, D_e is the

163 effective diffusion coefficient which can be computed by $D_e = \phi_f D_f / \tau_f$ with the

164 tortuosity of fracture $\tau_f = \phi^{-1/3}$ and the diffusion coefficient D_f . In the presence of a

165 sufficient quantity of solid reactants, the rate of acid-rock chemical reaction, R_m^{HCl} is
 166 determined by[49]:

$$167 \quad R_m^{HCl} = K(C^{HCl})^{n_a} \quad (8)$$

168 where n_a is the reaction order, and K the reaction rate constant calculated through

$$169 \quad K = Ae^{\frac{-E}{R_g T}} \quad (9)$$

170 where A is the Arrhenius constant, e the base of the natural logarithm, E the
 171 activation energy, R_g the molar gas constant, and T the absolute temperature. From
 172 Eq.(9), it can be seen that the increase of temperature can significantly improve the
 173 reaction rate between acid and rock matrix, and enhances the corrosion effect of acid
 174 on rock matrix. However, this is only limited to the change of matrix porosity, and the
 175 change of fracture opening caused by multi-field coupling needs to be analyzed by
 176 numerical simulation.

177 Besides the chemical reaction process, the transport of reactants and products in
 178 the fracture should be taken into account which is described by the following equation.

$$179 \quad d_f \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\phi_f C_f^{HCl}) + d_f \mathbf{v}_f \cdot \nabla_{\tau} C_f^{HCl} - d_f \nabla_{\tau} \cdot (D_e \nabla_{\tau} C_f^{HCl}) = -d_f R_f^{HCl} + Q_c \quad (10)$$

180 where R_f^{HCl} is the acid-rock reaction rate of fracture, Q_c is the mass flux from the
 181 porous matrix into the fracture.

182 Based on the Arrhenius equation (Eq.(9)), the chemical reaction rate exhibits an
 183 exponential increase with temperature[50-51]. However, it is widely believed that the
 184 acid-rock chemical reaction within fractures of high-temperature reservoirs is primarily
 185 governed by the mass transfer rate. Furthermore, when the fluid pressure exceeds 6

186 MPa, pressure variations also have an insignificant impact on the reaction rate[52].

187 Therefore, R_f^{HCl} can be determined based on mass transfer[35, 49].

$$188 \quad R_f^{HCl} = \kappa_c a_{vf} (C_f^{HCl} - C_s^{HCl}) \quad (11)$$

189 where κ_c is the mass transfer coefficient obtained by[49, 53]

$$190 \quad \kappa_c = 0.33 \frac{D_i^f}{d_f} N_{Re}^{0.5} N_{Sc}^{1/3} \quad (12)$$

191 with

$$192 \quad N_{Re} = \frac{\rho_{acid} d_f |\mathbf{v}_f|}{\mu_{acid}}, \quad N_{Sc} = \frac{\mu_{acid}}{\rho_{acid} D_i^f} \quad (13)$$

193 D_i^f is the solute diffusion coefficient in the fracture ($i = HCl$ or $CaCl_2$), N_{Re} is the

194 Reynolds number, N_{Sc} is the Schmidt number, $a_{vf} = 2/d_f$ which is the interfacial

195 area per unit volume of fracture, and C_s^{HCl} is the HCl concentration at the fluid-solid

196 interface. Since $R_f^{HCl} = -k a_{vf} C_s^{HCl}$ for first-order kinetic reaction (k the reaction rate

197 constant), C_s^{HCl} can be expressed as[35].

$$198 \quad C_s^{HCl} = \frac{C_f^{HCl}}{1 + k/\kappa_c} \quad (14)$$

199 As $k \gg \kappa_c$ in the present process, from Eq. (14), $C_s^{HCl} \approx 0$, which indicates the

200 immediate consumption of acid upon transfer to the liquid-solid interface. Since the

201 rate of reaction is constrained by the rate of mass transfer herein, this reaction can be

202 classified as a mass transfer-controlled reaction.

203 The last term in Eq.(10), the mass flux, is computed using

$$204 \quad Q_c = \mathbf{n}_u \cdot (\mathbf{v}_m C^{HCl} - D_e \nabla C^{HCl}) \Big|_{up} + \mathbf{n}_d \cdot (\mathbf{v}_m C^{HCl} - D_e \nabla C^{HCl}) \Big|_{down} \quad (15)$$

205 2.3 Heat transfer

206 The assumption of water-rock thermal equilibrium is adopted, i.e. the temperature
 207 of water and nearby rock is assumed to be the same. Considering heat convection, heat
 208 conduction, and heat source from the reaction, the energy conservation equation can be
 209 obtained.

210 For rock matrix[11],

$$211 \quad (\rho c_p)_{eff,m} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_{acid} c_{p,acid} \mathbf{v}_m \cdot \nabla T - \nabla \cdot \lambda_{eff,m} \nabla T = Q_m^{chem} \quad (16)$$

212 where $(\rho c_p)_{eff,m} = \phi_m \rho_{acid} c_{p,acid} + (1 - \phi_m) \rho_s c_{p,s}$ is the effective volumetric heat
 213 capacity of the rock matrix, $\lambda_{eff,m} = \phi \lambda_{acid} + (1 - \phi) \lambda_s$ the effective thermal conductivity
 214 of the rock matrix, ρ the effective density of the rock matrix, c_p the effective heat
 215 capacity at constant pressure, T the temperature, and Q_m^{chem} the heat source from
 216 chemical reaction given by[49]:

$$217 \quad Q_m^{chem} = -R_m^{HCl} H \quad (17)$$

218 where H is the enthalpy of the reaction which is negative since the acid-rock reaction
 219 is exothermic.

220 The energy conservation equation for fracture is

$$221 \quad d_f (\rho c_p)_{eff,m} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + d_f \rho_{acid} c_{p,acid} \mathbf{v}_f \cdot \nabla T - \nabla \cdot (d_f \lambda_{eff,m} \nabla T) = d_f Q_f^{chem} + Q_T \quad (18)$$

222 where $(\rho c_p)_{eff,m} \approx \rho_{acid} c_{p,acid}$ is the effective volumetric heat capacity of fracture,
 223 $\lambda_{eff,m} \approx \lambda_{acid}$ the effective thermal conductivity of fracture, and Q_f^{chem} the reaction heat
 224 source in fracture as follows:

$$225 \quad Q_f^{chem} = -R_f^{HCl} H \quad (19)$$

226 Q_T is the heat source term from the matrix to fracture.

227
$$Q_T = \mathbf{n}_u \cdot (\rho_{acid} c_{p,acid} \mathbf{v}_m T - \lambda_{eff,m} \nabla T) \Big|_{up} + \mathbf{n}_d \cdot (\rho_{acid} c_{p,acid} \mathbf{v}_m T - \lambda_{eff,m} \nabla T) \Big|_{down} \quad (20)$$

228 2.4 Deformation of the rock matrix and fracture

229 For rock material, the application of linear elasticity (Hooke's law) and small
 230 deformation theory is appropriate to derive the equilibrium equation for the deformation
 231 of the rock matrix under purely gravitational loading conditions, which is expressed as
 232 follows:

233
$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho_{av} \mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (21)$$

234 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress vector, and $\rho_{av} = \phi_m \rho_{acid} + (1 - \phi_m) \rho_s$ refers to the average
 235 density of the rock matrix.

236 Due to the existence of pore water in the porous rock matrix, the total stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$
 237 can be expressed as:

238
$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el} - \alpha_B (p - p_{ref}) \mathbf{I} \quad (22)$$

239 where p_{ref} is the reference pressure, and \mathbf{I} the identity matrix. Based on the linear
 240 elastic model, the elastic stress vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}$ can be obtained through

241
$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{el} \quad (23)$$

242 where \mathbf{C} is the fourth-order elastic matrix tensor. Taking into account the thermal
 243 expansion, the elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{el}$ is equal to the total strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ minus the thermal strain
 244 $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t = \alpha_T (T - T_{ref})$, as follows.

245
$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{el} = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla^T \mathbf{u}) = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \alpha_T (T - T_{ref}) \quad (24)$$

246 where α_T is the coefficient of volumetric thermal expansion and T_{ref} the reference
 247 temperature.

248 Substituting Eqs. (22)-(24) into Eq. (21), the deformation equation for the rock
 249 matrix is obtained.

$$250 \quad (L+G)\nabla\theta + G\nabla^2\mathbf{u} - \alpha_B\nabla p - K_v\alpha_T\nabla T + \rho_{av}\mathbf{g} = 0 \quad (25)$$

251 where L and G are the Lamé constants, $\theta = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z}$ the volumetric strain,

252 \mathbf{u} the displacement vector, and K_v the volumetric modulus.

253 For fracture, as its dimensions are notably smaller in comparison to the dimensions
 254 of the surrounding matrix, the fracture can be simplified to a lower-dimensional, thin
 255 elastic layer characterized by a specific nominal thickness in numerical modeling (Fig.
 256 1). The fracture layer follows Hooke's law, thus[48],

$$257 \quad \mathbf{u}_u - \mathbf{u}_d - \mathbf{u}_0 = -\mathbf{F} / \mathbf{k}_A \quad (26)$$

258 where \mathbf{F} is a force/unit area, \mathbf{u}_u and \mathbf{u}_d the displacement vectors at the upper and
 259 lower boundaries of the fracture layer respectively, and \mathbf{u}_0 the initial compensation
 260 displacement.

261 The stiffness \mathbf{k}_A can be obtained using the normal stiffness, k_n , and the
 262 tangential stiffness, k_s , which characterize the deformation in the two corresponding
 263 directions, respectively:

$$264 \quad \mathbf{k}_A = k_n \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} + k_s (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}) \quad (27)$$

265 where \mathbf{n} the unit normal vector of the fracture. The normal and tangential stiffness
 266 of the thin elastic layer can be computed by its material parameters:

$$267 \quad k_n = \frac{E_f(1-\nu_f)}{d_f(1+\nu_f)(1-2\nu_f)}, \quad k_s = \frac{G_f}{d_f} \quad (28)$$

268 where E_f is the elastic modulus, ν_f the Poisson's ratio, and G_f the shear modulus.

269 2.5 Chemical corrosion of rock

270 The acid-rock chemical reaction leads to an increase both in the porosity of the
271 rock matrix and the aperture of fracture, and thus, enlarges the permeability of the
272 carbonate geothermal reservoir. For the rock matrix, the connection between porosity
273 variation and the reaction can be described through the continuity equation of the rock
274 skeleton as follows[54]:

$$275 \quad \frac{\partial \phi_m^{chem}}{\partial t} = \frac{R_m^{HCl}}{2\rho_s \omega} \quad (29)$$

276 where ϕ_m^{chem} is the matrix porosity caused by chemical reaction, $\omega = \zeta/M$
277 represents the molar number of CaCO_3 in a unit mass of rock. ζ and M denote the
278 content and molar mass of CaCO_3 minerals in the reservoir, respectively.

279 In addition, the change of the porosity attributed to thermo-pore elasticity effects
280 can be formulated as follows[55-56].

$$281 \quad \frac{\partial \phi_m^{mech}}{\partial t} = (\alpha_{Bm} - \phi_m^{mech}) \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{K_s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right) - (1 - \phi_m^{mech}) \alpha_T \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (30)$$

282 where ε_v is the volumetric strain and K_s is the stiffness in the tangential direction.

283 Combining Eqs. (29) and (30), the matrix porosity obtained with coupled THMC
284 modeling is

$$285 \quad \phi_m = \phi_m^{chem} + \phi_m^{mech} \quad (31)$$

286 The permeability of a rock matrix at a time point can be determined based on the
287 cubic law[49].

288
$$k_m = k_{m0} \left(\frac{\phi_m}{\phi_{m0}} \right)^3 \quad (32)$$

289 where k_{m0} is the initial permeability of the matrix.

290 For fracture, the rate of change in fracture aperture due to chemical corrosion can
 291 be calculated as[35, 54, 57]

292
$$\frac{\partial d_f^{chem}}{\partial t} = \frac{R_f^{HCl}}{2a_{vf} \rho_s \omega} \quad (33)$$

293 Furthermore, the change in fracture aperture due to the mechanical deformation
 294 can be computed using the parameters and normal strain of the thin elastic layer along
 295 with the fluid pressure in fracture[48].

296
$$d_f^{mech} = \left[1 + (\varepsilon_f^n - \varepsilon_{f0}^n) + (1 + \nu_f)(1 - 2\nu_f) \frac{p - p_0}{E_f(1 - \nu_f)} \right] d_{f0} \quad (34)$$

297 The fracture aperture under THMC coupling is finally obtained by integrating
 298 Eqs.(33) and (34),

299
$$d_f = d_f^{mech} + d_f^{chem} \quad (35)$$

300 The permeability of fracture can be calculated using the model of parallel plate
 301 flow[48]

302
$$k_f = \frac{d_f^2}{12} \quad (36)$$

303 2.6 THMC coupling relationship

304 The coupled THMC model incorporating multiple mechanisms has been
 305 established in Section 2.1 to Section 2.5, whose coupling relationship is summarized in
 306 Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 THMC coupling relationship

307
308

309 3. Model implementation and verification

310 3.1 Model implementation

311 The COMSOL software using the finite element method is applied for the
312 numerical computation of THMC modeling given its advantages in multiphysics
313 simulation, despite the capabilities of meshless methods in solving discontinuous and
314 fluid problems [58-62].

315 This study considers the influence of discrete fracture networks (DFNs) in acid
316 fracturing which are randomly generated with the length adhering to the power law and
317 orientation following Fisher distribution. The physical module of “Darcy's Law” is used
318 to calculate the acid flow rate in both the matrix (Eq. (1)) and fracture (Eq. (2)). The
319 module for “Transport of Diluted Species in Porous Media” is utilized to compute
320 solute concentrations within the matrix (Eq. (7)) as well as fracture (Eq. (10)). To
321 determine the temperature distribution in the matrix (Eq. (16)) and fracture (Eq. (18)),
322 the module titled “Heat Transfer in Porous Media” module is employed. Further, the
323 “Solid Mechanics” module is applied to acquire the deformation of both the matrix (Eq.
324 (21)) and fracture (Eq. (26)). Subsequently, to obtain the evolution of matrix porosity

325 (Eq. (29)) owing to chemical corrosion, the module of Domain ordinary differential
 326 equations (ODEs) and differential algebraic equations (DAEs) is enabled. For the
 327 change of fractures aperture (Eq. (33)), the Boundary ODEs and DAEs module are
 328 activated. The operation process and the selection of simulation modules in the software
 329 are summarized in Fig. 3.

330 For the modeling, the computational domain is discretized using free triangular
 331 mesh. The calculation starts with a default initial step and the variables are updated with
 332 an implicit backward difference formula. To enhance the convergence of computation
 333 for the proposed model, the separated coupling solver is adopted. All the analyses are
 334 conducted on a desktop computer with Intel i7 CPU and 16 GB RAM. On average, each
 335 simulation requires approximately thirty minutes to run, a duration mainly constrained
 336 by the computer's configuration and also influenced by the complexity of DFN.

337
 338 Fig. 3 Operation process and module selection of THMC coupling model

339 3.2 Model verification

340 To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed THMC model, it is first applied
341 to study a Thermo-Hydro (TH) coupling problem of heat extraction through heat-
342 carrying fluids in hot rocks[63-66]. Further, the problem of thermal consolidation of a
343 soil column with pore water, a classic Thermo-Hydro-Mechanical (THM) coupling
344 example[56, 63-64, 67-68], is analyzed. For both computations, the numerical results
345 exhibit good agreement with the analytical solutions, indicating the validity of the
346 coupled model for TH and THM simulations. As previous similar calculations by Liu
347 et al.[64-65] can be referred to, they are not presented here to avoid redundancy.
348 Thereafter, to test the capability for chemical analysis, a benchmark problem of solute
349 transport in an aquifer (Hydro-Chemical coupling) is studied in which the diffusion and
350 dispersion of solution are taken into account (see section 3.2.1). Further, to
351 comprehensively demonstrate the ability of the proposed THMC model, an actual
352 carbonatite geothermal field is leveraged to explore the multiple-physics evolution of
353 fracture aperture during acid fracturing (section 3.2.2).

354 3.2.1 Solute transport in an aquifer (HC coupling)

355 Fig. 4 shows the top view of the aquifer with 4000 m length in both dimensions
356 (not shown in full size due to large dimensions), and the groundwater flows from the
357 top left to the bottom right as indicated by the arrows. A circular injection region of
358 arbitrary solute with a radius of 44 m is created whose center is located at $x_0 = 0$ m, y_0
359 $= 0$ m (point #2). Besides Point #2, there are another three points used as the monitoring
360 points, involving point #1 ($x = -100$ m, $y = 100$ m), #3 ($x = 100$ m, $y = -100$ m) and #4

361 $(x = 200 \text{ m}, y = -200 \text{ m})$. For direct comparison, the parameters used in the numerical
 362 model (see Table 1) are the same as those in a previous analytical study[35] where the
 363 analytical solution of this problem is available.

364 The initial concentration distribution of solute in Fig. 4 is determined by [35]:

$$365 \quad c = c_0 \frac{1}{2\pi r^2} e^{-\frac{(x-x_0)^2+(y-y_0)^2}{2r^2}} \quad (37)$$

366 where c is concentration, C_0 the concentration of the injected solution and r denotes
 367 the radius of the injection region. There is no further injection afterward and the
 368 simulation duration spans 2000 days. The final distribution of solute concentration is
 369 presented in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 (a) illustrates the evolution of solute concentration at four
 370 monitoring points for both analytical and numerical solutions which are very close. The
 371 concentration of the solute increases and then decreases. The closer to the injection
 372 point, the greater the variation of concentration. Fig. 5 (b) presents the comparison of
 373 the concentration profiles along the line through the monitoring points at various time
 374 obtained by the analytical calculation and numerical simulation, which are quite close.
 375 The maximum concentration experiences a gradual decrease as the transport of solute
 376 through the groundwater.

377 Table 1 Input parameters of the coupled model for solute transfer problem[35]

Parameters	Values [unit]
Porosity of fracture	1
Diffusion coefficient of solute	$10^{-9} \text{ [m}^2/\text{s]}$
Longitudinal dispersion coefficient of solute	100 [m]
Transverse dispersion coefficient of solute	10 [m]
Velocity of groundwater	0.1 [m/d]
Injection position	$(x = 0 \text{ m}, y = 0 \text{ m})$
Injection concentration	1000 [mol/m ³]

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379
380

Fig. 4 Solute concentration distribution for 2000 days (time history of concentration extracted at monitoring points)

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382
383

Fig. 5 Solute concentration comparison between numerical results and analytical solutions: (a) time history at different locations; (b) distribution along observation line at different time

384 3.2.2 Evolution of fracture aperture (THMC coupling)

385 Well D22 of Rongcheng carbonatite geothermal field located in Xiong'an New
386 Area, China[69-71], is chosen herein to investigate the evolution of fracture aperture
387 during acid fracturing. Fig. 6(a) shows the geographical and geological information
388 around this experimental well. The fracturing process, following the injection of prepad
389 fluid, was done by alternately injecting gelled water and gelled acid. The geothermal
390 reservoir contains numerous intricate natural fractures. To facilitate the analysis of the
391 selected large 2-D square area with a side length of 1400 m (Fig. 6(b)), five major
392 fractures are identified and labeled I to V. Following previous studies[31, 69-71], the
393 initial aperture of the fractures is 0.279 mm. Boundary conditions assign normal

394 displacement constraints on the left and lower boundaries, while the upper and right
 395 boundaries experience maximum and minimum horizontal stresses of 73.25 MPa and
 396 53.4 MPa, respectively. The initial pressure is set at 29.8 MPa and the initial
 397 temperature of the model is 78°C. The injection well is on fracture I, through which the
 398 fracturing fluid is injected with a constant temperature of 32°C and a fixed
 399 concentration of 4297.5 mol/m³, adhering to the practical injection rate throughout the
 400 working process (Fig. 7). The remaining parameters are consistent with those in Section
 401 4. The computational domain is finely discretized using 54744 unstructured triangular
 402 meshes. Note that adequate calculation steps are taken before the injection to achieve
 403 an equilibrium initial state of in-situ stress.

404
 405 *Fig. 6 Schematic diagram of the actual case study (a) geographical and geological information around well*
 406 *D22[71] and (b) geometry and boundary conditions of the computational model with I to V the five major fractures*

407 Fig. 7 compares the time history of net wellhead pressure obtained from field tests
 408 and numerical computation, which changes with the variation of injection rate. The trend
 409 of the calculation result is comparable with the in-situ monitored data. The simulation
 410 exhibits insensitivity to the fluctuations of injection rate, particularly when the injection

411 rate approaches zero. This phenomenon is primarily attributed to the simplification of
412 the numerical model, which considers only five major fractures, meanwhile reducing
413 the 3-D problem to a 2-D problem. Fig. 8 illustrates the temporal evolution of the
414 maximum fracture aperture for fractures I to V over the process of fracturing. Fractures
415 I, III, and IV display observable aperture increases as they are near the injection well,
416 and also there is good connectivity among them. Fracture I has the most significant
417 change, around 0.87 mm, followed by fractures III and IV at approximately 0.51 mm
418 and 0.17 mm, respectively: the closer to the injection well, the larger the aperture
419 increase is. Regarding to fractures II and V, which are situated farther from the injection
420 well and present poorer connectivity with other fractures, show negligible changes in
421 aperture.

422 To further investigate, fracture I is selected to examine its spatial and temporal
423 evolution of aperture, as shown in Fig. 9. As the distance from the injection well
424 increases, the aperture initially enlarges before diminishing. The fracture intersections
425 with fractures III and IV experience minor changes in the trend of spatial aperture
426 variation due to the dispersion of fracturing fluid caused by intersecting fractures.
427 Additionally, although the aperture increases over time, the extent of the change varies
428 depending on the stage of the fracturing process. For instance, from 40 to 80 min, the
429 injection is mainly for the prepad fluid (see Fig. 7), which leads to a small rise of
430 aperture; while from 160 to 200 min, the acid rock reaction results in a significant
431 increase.

432
433

Fig. 7 Comparison for dynamic analysis of net wellhead pressure in field test and simulation

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Fig. 8 Evolution of maximum aperture for fractures I to V

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437

Fig. 9 Spatial and temporal evolution of aperture for fracture I

438 4. Numerical simulations and sensitivity analyses

440
441
442

Fig. 10 Boundary conditions of THMC fields

Table 2 Parameters used in the simulation[31, 69, 72-73]

Category	Parameters	Values [unit]
Rock matrix	Young modulus	50 [GPa]
	Poisson's ratio	0.25
	Density	2600 [kg/m ³]
	Biot's ratio	0.66
	Initial porosity	0.05
	Initial permeability	20 [mD]
	Thermal expansion coefficient	5×10 ⁻⁶ [1/K]
	Specific heat capacity	880 [J/kg/K]
	Thermal conductivity	1.57 [W/m/K]
Fracture	Young modulus for fracture	50 [MPa]
	Storage coefficient	1×10 ⁻⁸ [1/Pa]
	Initial aperture	1 [mm]
Acidizing fluid	Permeability	Cubic law
	Initial temperature	293.15 [K]
	Density	1192 [kg/m ³]
	Viscosity	0.005 [Pa·s]
	Compressibility	4.4×10 ⁻¹⁰ [1/Pa]
	Thermal conductivity	0.6 [W/m/K]

	Specific heat capacity	4182 [J/kg/K]
	Diffusion coefficient	1.15×10^{-10} [m ² /s]
	Injection concentration	8750 [mol/m ³]
Reaction	Reaction order	0.6
	Content of CaCO ₃ minerals	100%
	Forward activation energy	53208.77 [J/mol]
	Preexponential factor	27529.13 [1/s]
	Reaction enthalpy	-20 [kJ/mol]

443

444 This section conducts the numerical computation and sensitivity analyses of the
445 coupled THMC model. A plane strain square rock of dimensions of 200 m in both
446 directions is used for the study. Fig. 10 shows the boundary conditions for (a) Thermal
447 module (T), (b) Hydraulic module (H), (c) Mechanical module (M), and (d) Chemical
448 module (C). The temperature at the left boundary remains constant at 80 °C, while the
449 other three boundaries are insulated. The left boundary is given a constant inflow rate,
450 and the right boundary is under a constant pressure of 10 MPa. The left and right
451 boundaries are rollers, and the lower boundary is fixed. Furthermore, the upper
452 boundary is subjected to a uniformly distributed external load. Note that adequate
453 calculation steps are taken before the injection to achieve an equilibrium initial state of
454 in-situ stress. For the chemical field, the acid liquid is injected from the left boundary
455 with a constant concentration, while the other three boundaries are impermeable. The
456 parameters of the numerical model are shown in Table 2.

457 A fracture network is added in the computational domain. The length of the
458 fracture obeys the exponential distribution law and the dip angle of the fracture is
459 considered to be random and uniform along the fracture. As shown in Fig. 11, two

460 different discrete fracture networks are generated. The first discrete fracture network
 461 (DFN_1) shown in Fig. 11(a) consists of 40 fractures with lengths ranging from 50 m
 462 to 100 m. In this case, the domain is meshed using 82,734 free triangular elements. For
 463 the second discrete fracture network (DFN_2) in Fig. 11(b), there are 80 fractures with
 464 the minimum length being 20 m and maximum length of 100m. The simulation model
 465 is discretized with 97,524 free triangular elements. For direct comparison, the locations
 466 of the six observation points (points #1 to #6) and the size and location of the two
 467 observation fractures (fractures #1 and #2) in these two fracture networks are the same,
 468 which benefits the following comparative analyses.

469
 470 *Fig. 11 Geometry of natural fracture networks with different fracture numbers and sizes*

471 4.2 Evaluation of the acid fracturing effect

472 Through 120-min continuous injection of 26.8% HCl (8750 mol/m^3) at a rate of
 473 $Q_{inj} = 2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$, Fig. 12 shows the distribution of pressure, acid concentration,
 474 temperature, and chemical aperture (aperture generated by chemical reaction) for the
 475 DFN_1 at four different moments, i.e. 30 min, 60 min, 90 min, and 120 min. The results
 476 vary with time as the injection of acid. At 30 min, the pressure in most areas of the field

477 is above 30 MPa with the highest local pressure reaching around 45MPa. Over time,
478 the pressure gradually decreases and the overall value becomes close to the initial
479 pressure of 10MPa. Concerning the concentration of acid, at 30 min of injection, the
480 concentration is higher in the fractures near the inflow boundary which can reach 8750
481 mol/m³. Later, as the solute diffuses, the acid concentration in the inside fractures
482 connected to those near the inflow region gradually increases. On the other hand, for
483 the fractures not connected, the acid concentration changes minimally. From the
484 temperature figures, it is clear that the temperature at most of the fractures is close to
485 the initial reservoir temperature of 80 °C, while for a small number of fractures, the
486 temperature is lower due to the injection of low-temperature acid liquid. The
487 interconnection between the fractures improves the flow of liquid in the network which
488 increases the reaction rate. In this case, the fracture corrosion becomes faster which
489 enhances convection, and thus the fracture temperature decreases rapidly. Further, as
490 time passes, the chemical aperture gradually increases, some of which can reach about
491 5 mm. Identifying these fractures with large chemical apertures reveals their
492 fundamental consistency to those observed in the temperature figures under reduced
493 temperatures, which is due to chemical corrosion. Note that the change in fracture
494 aperture is influenced not only by initial aperture but also by factors such as pore
495 pressure and temperature. Among these factors, the effect of temperature is less because
496 of the short duration of temperature exposure and limited heat transfer. Also, the thermal
497 expansion of the matrix is smaller than the deformation of the fracture.

498

499

Fig. 12 Distribution of pressure, acid concentration, temperature, and chemical aperture of DFN_1 at different time

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501

About DFN_2, Fig. 13 presents the pressure distribution, acid concentration,

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temperature, and chemical aperture at different time points. The overall results of

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DFN_2 exhibit similarity to those of DFN_1. Whereas, the maximum pressure in the

504

model of DFN_2, close to 50 MPa, is larger than that of DFN_1. In addition, there is

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also a slight difference in the maximum value of the chemical aperture, which is around

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4 mm for DFN_2, smaller than that of DFN_1. This is mainly because the average

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fracture length in DFN_2 is shorter. Thus, the smaller contact area of reactants reduces

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the acidification reaction.

509

510

511

Fig. 13 Distribution of pressure, acid concentration, temperature, and chemical aperture of DFN_2 at different time

512

For a more precise description of the concentration variations in the reactant HCl

513

and the product CaCl₂, distinct observation fractures, namely fracture #1, are selected

514

from the two fracture networks for detailed examination. In Fig. 14(a) for DFN_1, as

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the injection of the reactant HCl progresses along the fractures and undergoes

516

consumption, its concentration experiences a decline. In the initial stages within DFN_1,

517

there is a pronounced reduction in the concentration of reactants, marked by a swift

518

occurrence of an inflection point, followed by a plateau in the change. As the acid-rock

519

reaction becomes increasingly adequate, the point of zero HCl concentration advances.

520

Specifically, at the 20-minute mark, the zero concentration point for the reactants is

521

situated at approximately 40 m, and by the 120-minute interval, the HCl concentration

522 reaches zero at around 30 m. As shown, the product CaCl_2 concentration in DFN_1
523 generally increases and then decreases. The increase is due to the onset of the acid rock
524 reaction, while the decrease is due to the gradual flow of products out of the fracture.
525 The CaCl_2 concentration along observation fracture #1 increases slowly at 20 min but
526 decreases to zero at approximately 40 m. From 40 min to 120 min, the product
527 concentration increases rapidly, rises slowly to a peak at approximately 2.5 m, and then
528 decreases slowly. Meanwhile, the peak value increases with time. As depicted in Fig.
529 14(b), the CaCl_2 concentration in DFN_1 exhibits a general trend of initial increase
530 followed by subsequent decrease. This rise is attributed to the initiation of the acid rock
531 reaction, while the subsequent decline is a consequence of the gradual outflow of
532 products from the fracture. Specifically, along observation fracture #1, there is a gradual
533 ascent in CaCl_2 concentration over the initial 20 minutes, culminating in a subsequent
534 decline to zero around the 40-minute mark. Subsequently, over the duration of 40 to
535 120 min, there is a rapid increase in product concentration, reaching a peak at
536 approximately 2.5 m, and subsequently displaying a gradual decline. Concurrently, the
537 peak value demonstrates an upward trajectory over time.

538 Concerning DFN_2, in Fig. 14(c), the concentration distributions of HCl along
539 observation line #1 exhibit minimal variation across different time points. The curves
540 can be categorized into four phases. Initially, up to the fracture intersection point at 30
541 m, the concentration curve displays a gradual and linear decrease. At the intersection
542 point, there is a more pronounced decline in HCl concentration, accompanied by an

543 increased slope, indicative of heightened fluid flow rates. Moving from the intersection
544 point to the termination of the fracture at 50 m, the concentration curve experiences a
545 non-linear decrease. Subsequently, as the reactants approach the fracture's dead-end,
546 the rate of fluid flow decreases, and convection becomes the predominant mechanism
547 governing material transport, resulting in a gradual reduction of reactant concentration
548 towards zero. Fig. 14(d) illustrates the evolution of CaCl_2 concentration, also divisible
549 into four stages. Before the intersection point, there is a gradual increase in product
550 concentration as the reaction progresses. Post the intersection point, the concentration
551 undergoes a rapid ascent followed by a slower rise to reach a peak. Notably, the peak
552 value reduces over time. After this peak, as the HCl concentration approaches zero, the
553 reaction rate decreases to zero, leading to the cessation of the reaction and the eventual
554 reduction of CaCl_2 concentration to zero.

555

556

557

558

Fig. 14 Spatial and temporal distributions of concentration for reactant HCl and product CaCl₂ at different time

559

for observation line #1 of DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row)

560

The chemical aperture of the fracture is linked to the extent of chemical reactions.

561

Fig. 15 presents the spatial and temporal distribution of the chemical aperture

562

concerning observation fractures #1 and #2 within the two fracture networks. For

563

fracture #1, its variation in chemical aperture distinctly differs between the two fracture

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networks. As illustrated in Fig. 15(a), within DFN_1, there is a general tendency for the

565

chemical aperture to decrease, reaching zero at approximately 30 m. Notably, the

566

leftmost end of the fracture exhibits an increasing chemical aperture over time. In

567

contrast, as shown in Fig. 15(c), within DFN_2, the chemical aperture undergoes a more

568

gradual reduction compared to DFN_1. Subsequently, it rapidly decreases to zero at the

569

termination of the fracture. Concurrently, at the leftmost end of the fracture, the

570

chemical aperture surpasses that of DFN_1. This discrepancy is primarily attributable

571

to variations in the acid flow rates within the fractures. Observation fracture #1 in

572

DFN_2 is interconnected with other fractures, resulting in a higher flow rate, and

573

consequently, a heightened reaction rate and a larger chemical aperture at the same

574

injection rate. Conversely, observation fracture #1 in DFN_1 is entirely isolated,

575 leading to a lower flow rate, a more modest reaction rate, and a smaller chemical
576 aperture.

577 Regarding observation fracture #2, the chemical aperture experiences an
578 incremental rise from zero in both scenarios, as this fracture is situated at a distance
579 from the reactant injection boundary. In Fig. 15(b), within DFN_1, the chemical
580 aperture exhibits an exceedingly slow increase up to 40 m. Subsequently, there is an
581 accelerated growth in chemical aperture near the fracture intersection. Over time, the
582 amplitude of change becomes more pronounced, and the peak attains a higher value.
583 Meanwhile, as presented in Fig. 15(d), the peak values at each moment within DFN_2
584 are consistently smaller than their counterparts in DFN_1. This discrepancy can be
585 attributed to the larger flow rate within DFN_2, leading to an accelerated reaction rate
586 and consequently a more substantial chemical aperture.

589

590 *Fig. 15 Spatial and temporal distribution of chemical aperture of observation lines #1 and #2 of DFN_1 (the first*
 591 *row) and DFN_2 (the second row)*

592 Chemical reactions play an important role in inducing changes in the chemical
 593 aperture, and thus the total fracture aperture. Fig. 16, illustrates the histories of six
 594 observation points of both two fracture networks, presenting the variations in chemical
 595 aperture and total aperture over a span of 0 to 120 min. Chemical corrosion-induced
 596 alterations in fracture aperture are irreversible, leading to either an increase or
 597 maintenance of chemical apertures. In DFN_1, depicted in Fig. 16(a), the chemical
 598 aperture at observation points #1, #2, #4, and #6 exhibits notable temporal variations,
 599 with observation point #1 exhibiting the maximum and observation point #5 displaying
 600 the minimum chemical aperture. Regarding total aperture, as presented in Fig. 16(b),
 601 the curve demonstrates an overall trend of growth at most of the observation points.
 602 However, point #3 displays an increase followed by a decrease. Analysis in conjunction
 603 with Eq. (34) reveals that pressure is the dominant factor influencing the total aperture
 604 change at this point. In addition, the liquid subsequently diffuses in all directions,
 605 leading to pressure dissipation and rock matrix expansion. This dual effect causes the
 606 contraction of fractures, contributing to a reduction in total aperture. At observation

607 point #5, poor fracture connectivity results in minimal acid concentration and chemical
608 aperture. For this reason, along with the unchanged conditions such as temperature and
609 pressure, this point maintains an almost constant total fracture aperture. At any given
610 observation point and moment, a comparative analysis between chemical and total
611 apertures shows that total apertures surpass chemical apertures. This is because the
612 chemical apertures initiate from corrosion, while the total apertures possess an initial
613 value, stemming from the fracture's inherent aperture. Furthermore, the discrepancy
614 also arises from additional factors, such as mechanical apertures which influence the
615 total apertures.

616 For DFN_2, Fig. 16(c) shows that the progression of the chemical aperture closely
617 mirrors that of DFN_1. However, a distinguishing factor is observed wherein the
618 chemical aperture is maximal at observation points #1 and #2, and minimal at points #5
619 and #6 in DFN_2. This variance can be attributed primarily to the connectivity of
620 fractures. Points #1 and #2 exhibit enhanced fracture connectivity, leading to intensified
621 chemical reactions and thus larger chemical apertures. Conversely, points #5 and #6
622 display diminished chemical apertures. Examining Fig. 16(d), the overall shape of the
623 total aperture curve aligns closely with that of DFN_1. Specifically, observation point
624 #1 manifests the largest total aperture, while point #5 demonstrates the smallest total
625 aperture. The trend in the total fracture aperture at points #3 and #6 in DFN_2 is similar
626 to that observed at point #3 in DFN_1, which is due to the same reason as explained
627 above.

(a) DFN_1, chemical aperture

(b) DFN_1, total aperture

(c) DFN_2, chemical aperture

(d) DFN_2, total aperture

Fig. 16 Evolutions of chemical aperture and total aperture with time for six observation points in DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row)

Fig. 17 Influence of temperature, chemical reaction, and mechanics on aperture variation at Point #1 of DFN_2

To distinctly understand the individual effect of chemical reaction, mechanical and temperature on fracture aperture, numerical computations are conducted, each time excluding one of these factors. Considering the distance from monitoring fracture and

637 nearby fracture connectivity, Point #1 of DFN_2 is selected as the observation point to
638 effectively present the influences of the above-mentioned factors. As illustrated in Fig.
639 17, removing the chemical reaction results in an aperture increase of only 0.6 mm,
640 which is significantly smaller than that when the mechanical component is omitted.
641 According to Eqs.(33) to (35), the total fracture expansion is considerably influenced
642 by the interaction between chemical dissolution and erosion (positive contribution), and
643 mechanical stress constraints (negative contribution, whose removal also leads to a
644 larger initial aperture). Furthermore, it is evident that, without the influence of
645 temperature, the change in overall aperture is close to the result including all the factors,
646 indicating that temperature minimally contributes to the evolution of fracture in the
647 current situation, primarily through thermal expansion or thermal stress effects on the
648 rock. This result is consistent with the explanations of Eqs.(8) and (11) in Section 2.2.

649 4.3 Evaluation of injection rate effect

650 The average values of chemical aperture and pressure serve as primary parameters
651 for assessing the overall effect of the injection rate. At high reservoir temperatures, the
652 injection rate of fracturing fluid emerges as the predominant factor influencing the
653 chemical reaction rate. Consequently, the chemical reaction rate exerts an impact on
654 both the chemical aperture and pressure. In Fig. 18, the temporal evolutions of average
655 chemical aperture and pressure in two fracture networks across varying injection rates
656 of acidizing fluid are presented. As illustrated in Fig. 18(a) for DFN_1 and Fig. 18(c)
657 for DFN_2, the average chemical apertures exhibited increments of approximately 0.35

658 mm and 0.30 mm, respectively, within a 120-minute timeframe at an injection rate of
659 $Q_{inj} = 0.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$. Under an increased injection rate, $Q_{inj} = 2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$, the
660 average chemical apertures experienced greater increases, measuring about 0.70 mm
661 and 0.80 mm, respectively. Referencing Eq. (11) in Section 2.2, the total reaction rate
662 is constrained by the mass transfer rate, signifying a direct correlation between injection
663 rate and reaction rate—higher injection rates correspond to greater reaction rates.
664 However, as the injection rate increases monotonically, the average chemical aperture
665 exhibits a diminishing rate of increment, as shown in Fig. 18(a) and (c). This trend is
666 attributed to the coupled effects of multiple fields, as analyzed in Section 4.2, where
667 mechanical factors constrain the growth of the fracture aperture.

668 Analysis of Fig. 18(b) (DFN_1) and Fig. 18(d) (DFN_2) indicates a temporal
669 pattern wherein the average pressure exhibits an initial increase followed by a
670 subsequent decrease. Also, a positive correlation is discerned between the injection rate
671 and the magnitude of the peak of average pressure. This heightened pressure peak, in
672 turn, elevates the likelihood of fracture propagation. In addition, a notable inverse
673 relationship is identified, where higher injection rates correspond to shorter durations
674 to reach the pressure peak. Further, under a specific injection rate, the average pressure
675 peak of DFN_2 is generally larger than that of DFN_1. This discrepancy is mainly
676 ascribed to the difference in fracture connectivity.

677

678

679

680 Fig. 18 Evolutions of average chemical aperture and average pressure with time under different injection rates for
 681 DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row)

682 4.4 Evaluation of acid concentration effect

683 The acid concentration plays a pivotal role in dictating the chemical reaction rate
 684 and further influences the chemical aperture. Fig. 19 illustrates the temporal evolutions
 685 of the average chemical aperture and reaction rate for two fracture networks across
 686 varied injection concentrations. In 120 min, there is an upward trend in the average
 687 chemical aperture for both fracture networks. Notably, this increase is more pronounced
 688 with higher injection concentrations. This phenomenon is elucidated by Eq. (11) in
 689 section 2.2, indicating that, for a fixed volume of acidizing fluid, a higher acid

690 concentration intensifies the interaction between HCl and CaCO₃ molecules, leading to
691 a more vigorous chemical reaction and a significant rise in the chemical aperture. At
692 120 min, when the injection concentration is 8750 mol/m³, the average chemical
693 aperture attains its maximum, measuring approximately 0.7 mm for DFN_1 (Fig. 19(a))
694 and 0.8 mm for DFN_2 (Fig. 19(c)). This signifies an increase of approximately 118.8%
695 for DFN_1 and 128.6% for DFN_2 compared to the average chemical apertures at 120
696 minutes under an injection concentration of 2750 mol/m³. Similar to the effect of
697 injection rate discussed in the previous section, the final chemical aperture possesses a
698 non-linear increase with the monotone rise in acid concentration, and the phenomenon
699 is more pronounced with enhanced connectivity of fractures.

700 In Fig. 19(b) for DFN_1 and Fig. 19(d) for DFN_2, a similar pattern emerges in
701 the temporal evolution of the average reaction rate. Unlike the trend observed in the
702 average chemical aperture, the average reaction rate initially ascends and subsequently
703 descends over time. Concurrently, the peak value of the average reaction rate
704 demonstrates an augmentation corresponding to an increase in acid concentration.
705 Notably, for both fracture networks, the maximum average reaction rate of 3.2
706 mol/(m³·s) is recorded at an injection concentration of 2750 mol/m³, while at an
707 injection concentration of 8750 mol/m³, the average reaction rate achieves a peak of 8.5
708 mol/(m³·s), reflecting a substantial increase of approximately 165.6% compared to the
709 former. Despite variations in acid concentrations, the peak average reaction rate for a
710 given fracture network is reached at nearly the same moment, occurring at

711 approximately 27 min for DFN_1 and 38 min for DFN_2.

713
714 *Fig. 19 Evolutions of average chemical aperture and average reaction rate under different injection*
715 *concentrations of DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row) with time*

716 4.5 Evaluation of initial fracture aperture effect

717 Given that the initial aperture of fractures can impact the reactive surface area for
718 acid-rock interaction and potentially influence fluid mobility, its effects on the efficacy
719 of acid fracturing are worth studying. Under DFN_1 and DFN_2 with various initial
720 fracture apertures (0.6 mm, 0.8 mm, 1.0 mm and 1.2 mm), the temporal evolutions of
721 the average chemical aperture and the reaction rate are investigated, as illustrated in Fig.
722 20. As shown in Fig. 20 (a) and (c), for both DFNs, with the continuous injection of
723 acid fluid, the average chemical aperture keeps increasing over time. Nonetheless,

724 smaller initial apertures result in slightly larger mean chemical apertures, with the
725 maximum values reaching 0.72 mm and 0.83 mm for DFN_1 and DFN_2, respectively.
726 This is attributed to the difference in the reaction rate at rock surface, as a smaller initial
727 aperture can slow the acid flow, leading to a more concentrated distribution of acid in
728 the fractures. The phenomenon is consistent with the principles of Eqs.(11)-(13).
729 Additionally, better connectivity of the fractures (e.g. DFN_2) can improve the contact
730 between the acid fluid and rock surface within the fracture system, therefore promoting
731 the acid fracturing process.

732 In Fig. 20 (b) for DFN_1 and (d) for DFN_2, the average reaction rates initially
733 increase, with smaller initial apertures corresponding to higher peak average reaction
734 rates, whose maximum value approaches $10.8 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s})$. Furthermore, a smaller initial
735 fracture aperture extends the time required to reach the peak reaction rate: a small
736 aperture reduces the velocity of the acid solution, which hinders acid migration and
737 diffusion within the fractures, thus delaying the peak. Subsequently, the reaction rates
738 decrease and stabilize at approximately $2.2 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s})$ for DFN_1 and $3.1 \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s})$
739 for DFN_2, respectively. This behavior indicates that although the initial aperture
740 considerably affects early reaction rate, the dynamic equilibrium and self-regulating
741 mechanisms of the chemical reaction system finally converge the reaction rates to
742 similar stable values over time.

743

744

745

746

Fig. 20 Evolutions of average chemical aperture and average reaction rate under different initial fracture apertures of DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row) with time

747 4.6 Evaluation of reservoir temperature effect

748 Fig. 21 presents the time history of the average chemical aperture and reaction rate
 749 for two fracture networks under varying reservoir temperatures, illustrating the
 750 influence of reservoir temperature on acid fracturing. In Fig. 21 (a) and (c), the average
 751 chemical aperture shows a monotone increase across different temperatures for both
 752 DFNs. The thermal stress, induced by the temperature difference between the reservoir
 753 and the acid solution injected at a constant temperature of 20°C, can accelerate the
 754 reaction rate and enhance aperture growth. Therefore, as illustrated, a higher reservoir

755 temperature increases the magnitude of chemical aperture. The slight difference in the
756 fracturing results is owing to the short exposure duration and limited heat conduction.
757 At 120 min, the reservoir with a temperature of 120°C yields the maximum average
758 chemical apertures, approximately 0.73 mm for DFN_1 and 0.85 mm for DFN_2,
759 respectively. Again, better fracture connectivity contributes to larger chemical aperture
760 expansion.

761 The average reaction rates exhibit an initial increase followed by a decline during
762 the analysis, as shown in Fig. 21 (b) for DFN_1 and (d) for DFN_2. The peak reaction
763 rates for both fracture networks at various temperatures are comparable, which are
764 around 8.5 mol/(m³·s) for DFN_1 and 8.3 mol/(m³·s) for DFN_2, respectively,
765 indicating a mild impact of temperature variation on reaction rate. The later decline in
766 reaction rate can be influenced by the constraint from excessive thermal stress. As
767 temperature rises, a steeper temperature gradient causes uneven thermal expansion at
768 different locations within the rock, which generates high thermal stress. The excessive
769 stress weakens the acidizing effectiveness, as the acid struggles to effectively contact
770 the reactive rock surfaces. This explains the faster decline in reaction rate at high
771 temperatures.

Fig. 21 Evolutions of average chemical aperture and average reaction rate under different reservoir temperatures of DFN_1 (the first row) and DFN_2 (the second row) with time

5. Conclusions

In this study, a fully coupled THMC model for the acid fracturing process in carbonatite reservoirs is developed. The model integrates the interaction of heat transfer, acidizing fluid flow, deformation of the rock matrix and fractures, transport of reaction-diluted species as well as chemical corrosion phenomena. It is applied to quantify the effect of acid fracturing in carbonatite geothermal reservoirs. The current research delves into the evolution of crucial parameters such as pressure, acid concentration, temperature, and chemical aperture with time in different DFNs. The influences

784 imposed by injection rate, acid concentration, initial fracture aperture and reservoir
785 temperature on the efficiency of the acid fracturing process are also meticulously
786 analyzed. The key findings and conclusions drawn from this exploration are outlined
787 as follows.

788 a) Within a given fracture network, varying locations of fractures can result in
789 considerable differences in fracture apertures. For distinct fracture networks,
790 fractures at the same spatial location exhibit differing apertures under otherwise
791 identical conditions. The dissimilarity in connectivity between these fracture
792 networks leads to different flow rates and pressures. When subjected to an identical
793 injection rate, well-connected fractures experience a higher solute flow rate.
794 Conversely, poorly connected fractures exhibit lower solute flow rates,
795 contributing to pressure build-up and resulting in comparatively higher pressure
796 values.

797 b) The injection rate has a significant influence on the average chemical aperture,
798 with higher injection rates correlating with elevated average pressure peaks and a
799 reduced timeframe for inducing mechanical fracturing of the fractures. The acid
800 concentration of the HCl well impacts the change in the average reaction rate,
801 showing a positive correlation with the peak of the average reaction rate.
802 Consequently, acid concentration positively contributes to the average chemical
803 aperture. Over time, there is a decrease in the concentration of HCl, while the
804 concentration of the resulting product, CaCl_2 , experiences an initial increase

805 followed by a subsequent decrease. Also, it is found that the reaction rate is
806 inversely related to the initial fracture aperture, and thus, to the chemical aperture
807 growth as well. Moreover, the reservoir temperature mildly influences the chemical
808 expansion of fractures attributed to the short temperature exposure and limited heat
809 conduction. To sum up, the chemical factors play a substantial role in facilitating
810 fracture aperture, and the mechanical factors impose constraints on this process,
811 while the effect of temperature is relatively slight.

812 c) The limitation of this study lies in solely considering the corrosion of rock matrix
813 and fracture, the propagation of fracture is omitted which may happen in scenarios
814 of constant injection rate usually accompanied by pressure escalation. Further
815 investigation into the mechanisms of fracture propagation induced by acid
816 fracturing in carbonate geothermal reservoirs is warranted to enhance
817 understanding and guide engineering practices effectively. In addition, besides
818 accounting for the rapid change of acid concentration near the wellbore zone,
819 future efforts will be put into the exploration of diverse geological scenarios
820 integrated with detailed geological data from practical projects, including varying
821 lithologies and fault patterns, to enhance the applicability of the THMC model. The
822 uncertainty analysis for the sensitivity of the outcomes to the variations in input
823 parameters will also benefit the robustness of the model. Moreover, to better
824 capture the complexity of actual formation, the model will be developed into more
825 realistic 3-D simulation to enable improved analysis under actual working

826 conditions.

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